

EFFECT OF STRETCHING EXERCISES ON FLEXIBILITY AMONG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

Dr. Baiju A

Associate Professor of Physical Education, Mannaniya College of Arts and
Science, Pangode, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of stretching exercises on flexibility among football players. For the present study the 30 male football players from Mannaniya College of Arts and Science, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 25 years. For the present study pre test - post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen each. Group 'A' underwent stretching exercises only, group 'B' have not underwent any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA). The level of significance was set at 0.05. It was observed that the twelve weeks of stretching exercises have significantly improved the flexibility of football players.

Key Words: Stretching Exercises, Flexibility, Football Players.

Introduction:

Stretching is a physical exercise that requires putting a body part in a certain position that'll serve in the lengthening and elongation of the muscle or muscle group and thus enhance its flexibility and elasticity. Stretching is a common activity used by athletes, older adults, rehabilitation patients, and anyone participating in a fitness program. While the benefits of stretching are known, controversy remains about the best type of stretching for a particular goal or outcome. The purpose of this clinical commentary is to discuss the current concepts of muscle stretching interventions and summarize the evidence related to stretching as used in both exercise and rehabilitation. The duration of the hold of the stretch is irrelevant to notice improvement but rather how many times the stretch is repeated in a week. Its important to note that each muscle should be stretched only once and should be held for five minutes which is broken into five one-minute exercises or ten exercises of thirty seconds. The more we stretch in a week, the better the outcomes where according to certain studies stretching for more than three weeks served in decreasing stiffness and increasing the range of motion (two to eight-minute stretches served in increasing range of motion while ten minute stretches served in reobtaining normal range of motion). For individuals whose main objective is general fitness, it's recommended that static stretching should be done at least twice a week and stretch held for a minimum of 15 seconds followed by dynamic stretching. For older adults, the duration of static stretching should be longer to notice improvements. For example, a sixty-second hold stretch served in an increase by 2 degrees per week in range of motion while a thirty-second hold stretch served in an increase by 1 degree (Barosso et al. 2012).

For children, incorporating static stretching in physical education class significantly improved the flexibility of the hamstring muscles where four sessions per week served in a 17 degree increase in range of motion while two sessions per week improved the range of motion by 9 degrees. Pre-contraction stretching is a type of stretching that involves both the contraction and stretching of the muscle. It has been originally developed for the sole reason of relaxing muscles and increasing muscle tone. The most common type is PNF, proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation, which is a technique which can be performed in different ways. One of which is the contract-relax method during which the muscle is held in a stretching position by a partner and the person contracts the muscle for a minimum of 4 seconds followed by a short relaxation period of two to three seconds. The stretch should progressively be pushed further than the initial stretch and held for a longer period of time (held for a minimum of 10 seconds and relaxed for 20 seconds). Another would be hold-relax method which involves putting the muscle in a stretched position first by a partner and then the partner contracts the muscle while asking the person to prevent this contraction and afterwards passive stretch of the muscle is applied by the partner. A different method would be the contract-relax agonist contract during which the muscle is also elongated by the partner for a minimum of 4 seconds and the person is asked to contract the agonist of the muscle then activate the antagonist of the muscle followed by a relaxation period of 20 seconds.

The stretching of a muscle fiber begins with the sarcomere, the basic unit of contraction in the muscle fiber. As the sarcomere contracts, the area of overlap between the thick and thin myofilaments

increases. As it stretches, this area of overlap decreases, allowing the muscle fiber to elongate. Once the muscle fiber is at its maximum resting length (all the sarcomeres are fully stretched), additional stretching places force on the surrounding connective tissue. As the tension increases, the collagen fibers in the connective tissue align themselves along the same line of force as the tension. Therefore when you stretch, the muscle fiber is pulled out to its full length sarcomere by sarcomere, and then the connective tissue takes up the remaining slack. When this occurs, it helps to realign any disorganized fibers in the direction of the tension. This realignment is what helps in the rehabilitation of scarred tissue. When the muscle is stretched, so is the muscle spindle. The muscle spindle records the change in length (and how fast) and sends signals to the spine which convey this information. This triggers the stretch reflex which attempts to resist the change in muscle length by causing the stretched muscle to contract. The more sudden the change in muscle length, the stronger the muscle contractions will be (stretching exercises is based on this fact). This basic function of the muscle spindle helps to maintain muscle tone and to protect the body from injury. One of the reasons for holding a stretch for a prolonged period of time is that as you hold the muscle in a stretched position, the muscle spindle habituates and reduces its signalling. Gradually, you can train your stretch receptors to allow greater lengthening of the muscles (Barosso et al. 2012).

Reviews:

O'Sullivan (2009) warm-up and stretching are suggested to increase hamstring flexibility and reduce the risk of injury. This study examined the short-term effects of warm-up, static stretching and dynamic stretching on hamstring flexibility in individuals with previous hamstring injury and uninjured controls. A randomised crossover study design, over 2 separate days. Hamstring flexibility was assessed using passive knee extension range of motion (PKE ROM). 18 previously injured individuals and 18 uninjured controls participated. On both days, four measurements of PKE ROM were recorded: (1) at baseline; (2) after warm-up; (3) after stretch (static or dynamic) and (4) after a 15-minute rest. Participants carried out both static and dynamic stretches, but on different days. Data were analysed using Anova. Across both groups, there was a significant main effect for time ($p < 0.001$). PKE ROM significantly increased with warm-up ($p < 0.001$). From warm-up, PKE ROM further increased with static stretching ($p = 0.04$) but significantly decreased after dynamic stretching ($p = 0.013$). The increased flexibility after warm-up and static stretching reduced significantly ($p < 0.001$) after 15 minutes of rest, but remained significantly greater than at baseline ($p < 0.001$). Between groups, there was no main effect for group ($p = 0.462$), with no difference in mean PKE ROM values at any individual stage of the protocol ($p > 0.05$). Using ANCOVA to adjust for the non-significant ($p = 0.141$) baseline difference between groups, the previously injured group demonstrated a greater response to warm-up and static stretching, however this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.05$). Warm-up significantly increased hamstring flexibility. Static stretching also increased hamstring flexibility, whereas dynamic did not, in agreement with previous findings on uninjured controls. The effect of warm-up and static stretching on flexibility was greater in those with reduced flexibility post-injury, but this did not reach statistical significance. Further prospective research is required to validate the hypothesis that increased flexibility improves outcomes.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of stretching exercises on flexibility among football players. For the present study the 30 male football players from Mannaniya College of Arts and Science, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 25 years. For the present study pre test - post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen each. Group 'A' underwent stretching exercises only, group 'B' have not underwent any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA). The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Flexibility of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	35.44	35.14	BG	0.64	1	0.64	0.13
			WG	129.73	28	4.63	
Post Test Mean	40.98	35.40	BG	232.96	1	232.96	54.79*
			WG	119.05	28	4.25	
Adjusted Post Mean	40.93	35.45	BG	224.64	1	224.64	56.32*
			WG	107.67	27	3.98	

* Significant at 0.05 level,

Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20, 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of flexibility of experimental and control groups were 40.93 and 35.45 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 56.32 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result

of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on flexibility. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups differ significantly. The pre, post and adjusted post mean values of flexibility of both experimental and control groups are graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Flexibility of Experimental Group and Control Groups

Conclusion:

It was observed that the twelve weeks of stretching exercises have significantly improved the flexibility of football players.

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